

Lived Experiences of Junior High School Students undertaking
Modular Distance Learning Amidst
COVID-19: A Phenomenological Study

VILMA S. FERNANDO

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to investigate the lived experiences of Junior High School (JHS) students in public high school undertaking modular distance learning as COVID 19 pandemic caused tentative closure of schools. A qualitative phenomenological approach was used that focuses on the experiences of people, relying on data observed by the researcher mainly through semi-structured in-depth interviews and observation. Purposive sampling was utilized to select the twenty (20) participants in this study. Thematic analysis revealed five (5) clustered recurring themes in general: transfer of knowledge; communication issues; study mindset; quality of assessment; and Physioemotional Well-being. Participants' perception of the modular approach as difficult is attributed to their problems faced and coping mechanisms. These experiences stirred up adverse academic practices diminishing academic integrity while few participants adapted well to the new normal of learning. Yet, these learning experiences also caused exhaustion, emotional distraught and anxiety to most. Hence, it is recommended that learning activities and assessments need to be more student-centered, leading to independent thinking and lessons be designed, leveraging appropriate tools and instructional models that make students more engaged in the learning process.

INTRODUCTION

Lived Experiences of Junior High School Students undertaking Modular Distance Learning Amidst COVID-19: A Phenomenological Study

The COVID-19 pandemic has disrupted the Philippine Educational System. Consequently, public and private schools' closure has affected more than 1.2 billion learners worldwide, with more than 28 million learners in the Philippines (UNESCO, 2020). This compelled the Department of Education (DepEd) through DO 012 s. 2020 or the Basic Education Continuity Learning Plan (BE-LCP) to continue delivering quality education by conducting classes through the different Alternative Learning Delivery Modalities (LDMs) depending on COVID-19 restrictions and context of the community affected.

Thus, this has shifted students and teachers to study and work from home, which led to the delivery of Online Distance Learning (ODL), Modular Distance Learning (MDL), and TV/RadioBased Instruction (Quinones, 2020). Moreover, during the conduct of DepEd's National Learner Enrolment and Survey Forms (LESFs) last June to July, modular distance learning is preferred by 8.8 million out of the 22.2 million enrollees (39.6% of total respondents) for the upcoming school year (Malipot, 2020).

Though the two public secondary junior high schools in Balanga City, Bataan National High School and City of Balanga National High School adopted distance learning in different modalities, more than 80% of their whole student populace went for modular distance learning modality. In line with this, learning materials were prepared following the Department of Education's (DepEd) Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCS), printed, sorted, and distributed to learners through their parents because of mobility restriction due to COVID virus. As the classes resumed in October 2020, more challenges emerged but hopefully, these experiences would be learning opportunities for the learners as well. In essence, the major concern is still

leaning towards the learning of students. Is modular distance learning effective? In this view, the researcher is driven to study the lived experiences of junior high school students undertaking modular distance learning amidst the COVID-19 pandemic and its implications to their lives. The researcher believes that by studying their lived experiences, an authentic and evidence-based discovery about the situation and its implications to the students, their learning proficiency and disposition will be understood from a grassroots vantage point and not merely from a generic perspective despite the government's policies, plans, and programs to address the challenges brought by the pandemic to the education sector.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Modular learning is one of the types of distance learning that uses the Self-Learning Modules (SLMs) crafted based on the Department of Education's (DepEd) Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs). These modules include pre-test/diagnostic test, discussion of the topics, tasks, and series of activities and post-tests to attain the target skill or competency. Teachers then shall monitor the learners' progress via feedback mechanisms like Facebook messenger, email, phone/video call, or text message. However, not all of the feedback mentioned earlier is readily and easily accessible to students. So, home visitations are also an option if the students cannot access an internet connection, do not have a mobile load to participate or respond, or need special attention.

Though modular learning modality may seem popular at present, it has existed for a long time already. The modular approach dates back to 1950 as BF. Skinner's research led to the formulation of the different principles of teaching that later on became the main characteristics of programmed instruction, such as division of subject matter into smaller steps, immediate feedbacking, and self-pacing that are also the same principles used in module making (Molenda, 2008).

According to DepEd's Curriculum and Instruction Undersecretary Diosdado M. San Antonio, students still prefer modular distance learning from other options because SLMs which are K to 12 compliant, are developed following the Alternative Delivery Mode Learning Resources Standards. SLMs are designed to provide sufficient time for mastery and practice to ensure that the target skills (MELCs) are developed and achieved. In addition, a learner may adopt either Digital Modular Distance Learning (DMDL) or Printed Modular Distance Learning (PMDL). However, learners' preference in terms of Alternative Delivery Mode Learning may still vary on a case-to-case basis as learners with gadgets at home (laptops, desktops, tablets, smartphones) may

adopt DMDL by default. In contrast, learners without devices may have to settle with printed SLMs, for that matter. Then, teachers do timely appropriate monitoring and feedback for consultation and intervention purposes shall be put in place through various touch points such as text messaging and audio/video calls, whichever is available to the learner. If necessary and permitted, face-to-face interaction is utilized for this purpose. Training for family members and other community stakeholders as learning facilitators is done and provides learners with instructional support as needed in the absence of a classroom teacher (p. 6).

Aside from SLMs, Learning Activity Sheets (LAS) were made available for students too. DepEd Region 10 in its regional directive (RM 461, s.2020) states that learners shall use Weekly Learning Activity Sheets (WLAS) to complement the learners' textbooks. It shall contain activities and exercises as required in the competencies in MELCs.

Nevertheless, Modular Distance Learning is subjected to many challenges for both teachers and students. According to Araneta et al. (2020), as the Department of Education (DepEd) opens the "new normal" classes, they already received 16,000 complaints regarding blended learning, including reports of SLMs which the respective schools do not yet receive to be distributed to students.

According to the study of Dangle and Sumaoang (2020), learner-participants had difficulty in modular learning modality. Results showed that 90% of their participants had trouble answering their modules, and half of them did not finish all their modules in time within the allotted week. Furthermore, findings revealed that most of the students could not answer their modules independently, which is why the assistance of others is badly needed.

On the other hand, Suzanne Lischer's (2021) study about "Remote Learning and Students' Mental Health during the Covid-19 pandemic" suggests that students may be experiencing psychological effects from the outbreak of Covid-19, such as anxiety, fear, and worry, among

others (Cao et al.; Li et al.; and Wang et al. (2020). Yet, Lischer's survey showed that the students coped well with stresses that occurred during the lockdown. Moreover, most of the students felt well supported and expressed their appreciation of the lecturers. Additionally, Labrado et al. (2020) found out in their study that students learn with ease and thus become more autonomous because lessons are more simplified and are easier to follow.

Cognizant of this, Uddin Md. Akther (2013) stated that distance learning influenced time management skill development among students, though few of the respondents still had difficulty planning their "study" time. In support of this claim, Wilmot and Perkin (2011) concluded that modules positively affect student team working skills.

On the contrary, in Bhamani et al. 's (2020) study "Home Learning in Times of Covid," parent-respondents expressed that loss of interaction with peers and their typical environment had influenced the development of their children's social and emotional skills.

This was also highlighted in Al-dheleai and Tasir, Burdina, Krapotkina, and Nasyrova's (2020) study where loss of physical interaction between learners and teachers, and with difficulty of dealing with modules with limited or no one to turn to negatively impacted the quality of their work and learning.

Conceptual Framework

This study establishes a research focus on the lived experiences of Junior High School students and how they construct meaning of these experiences (Creswell, 2014). According to Bryman (2008), phenomenology is a "philosophy concerned with the question of how individuals make sense of the world around them. And how in particular, the philosopher should bracket out

preconceptions concerning their grasp of that world." It is also embedded within qualitative inquiry in general and endeavors to appreciate the "behavioral, emotive, and social meanings" that these lived experiences have for them (Guest, Namey, and Mitchell, 2013). For this matter, lived experiences pertain to how the Junior High School students perceive the shift in the pedagogical medium utilized and the challenges presented to them in all apparent facets. Tenets of phenomenology are entwined throughout the research design to ensure appropriate representation of the participants' lived experiences. Demonstrating the essence of the participants' perspective improves accuracy in representing the phenomenon (Moustakas, 1994).

The following diagram in figure 1 conceptualizes the study:

Figure 1:

Significance of the Study

The findings of this study will have a great value to the following:

Students. This would provide additional insights into developing their motivation and character through independent learning amidst the COVID-19 threat.

Teachers. It would serve as a guide to reflect and consider the students' perception of the learners' progressive appropriation of the educative process.

School Principals. Findings from this study may offer a solution/intervention for future decision-making to improve the distribution of SLMs/LAS to respective barangays, future planning in curriculum development, and future decisions on grant requests or purchase of other modular technology in their respective schools.

Department of Education. The results of this study may broaden their perspectives of what is happening on the grassroots level and may offer better options to address issues in modular learning.

Module writers. This is an opportunity to reflect and consider how the students are learning in the modular learning modality instead of the progressive enhancement of the said Alternative Learning Delivery Modalities.

Parents. This would serve as an indicator that their support in their children's learning through SLMs/LAS positively impacts their academic performance.

Future researchers. This would be another source of literature for related research.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

This study aims to describe the lived experiences of junior high school students in modular learning amidst COVID 19 pandemic. Distinctively, the study seeks to answer the following research questions:

1. How do junior high school students describe their experiences in Modular Distance Learning?
2. How do junior high school students understand the challenges of MDL amidst the pandemic?

3. What are the coping mechanism/s of junior high school students undertaking MDL to solve the challenges they've encountered?
4. What are the implications of MDL to the learning proficiency and dispositions of students?

SCOPE AND LIMITATION

This study aims to investigate the lived experiences of junior high school students in the province of Bataan, particularly those students enrolled in the public secondary high schools in Balanga City. Junior high school students' lived experiences of these and the challenges they experience will be explored and given a meaning that could augment in identifying and concretizing the perspectives and dispositions of students as well as their coping mechanisms that they have created and integrated into learning in the new normal. The participants of the study were Junior High School students in the two (20 Public Secondary High Schools in Balanga City selected through purposive sampling technique. At the time of the study, they are studying in Grades 7-10 for SY 2021-2022.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study utilized a qualitative phenomenological research design to understand people's experiences in a specific phenomenon. Thus, this phenomenological research aimed to describe the "lived experiences" of junior high school students undertaking modular distance learning. While it focused on the analysis of conscious and immediate lived experiences unique to each learner, it further sought reality from individuals' narratives of their experiences and feelings and thus produced in-depth descriptions of the phenomenon.

Instrument

The instrument which the researcher used in this study was an in-depth semi-structured interview guide. The interview guide as the research instrument of this study was subjected to a content validity test conducted by experts in the field.

SAMPLING

Participants

Participants of this study were twenty (20) selected Grades 7-10 Junior High School students from Bataan National High School and City of Balanga National High School through purposive sampling technique. These respondents are classified through modular distance learning as their learning modality and are currently studying in Balanga City in School Year 2021-2022.

Research Ethics

This study's permission and approval was obtained from the SDO of Balanga City and the School Principal, where the study was conducted. Once endorsed, the researcher started the indepth interviews with the selected junior high school students.

The first fundamental ethical consideration that was practiced is respect for confidentiality and anonymity procedures, which was explained in the letter to participate in the study. Their autonomy to participate was also taken into consideration.

An informed consent form was disseminated, indicating participants' permission to participate and other related essential activities such as audio recording and raising personal questions. Because of the COVID-19 threat, all interviews were done in a quiet, open room to observe safety measures and last up to two hours if necessary. It was conducted privately for the participants to share their lived experiences openly and freely in modular learning. Also, the researcher ensured that participants were not embarrassed, frightened, offended, or harmed.

As for confidentiality, the researcher protected the true identities of participants. Also, respondents' names were replaced with aliases or pseudonyms to ensure anonymity. Any additional identifiable information was removed in the transcription process. All the research data, including recordings, consent forms, interview transcripts, analyses, and electronic files, were kept and maintained for the sole purpose of this research.

Lastly, participants, data collection tools, and methodology were free from any form of biases (e.g., gender, class, ethnic, cultural biases). There were also no financial or other substantive conflicts of interest to influence the results or interpretation of the manuscripts. It was ascertained that the researcher has no interest in the outcomes of the study that may lead to the researcher's advantage (or benefit a member of the researcher's family and friends) and, therefore, compromise the integrity of the study. Thus, the outcomes of the study did not promote or appear to promote the researcher's personal or ideological beliefs.

DATA COLLECTION

Data Gathering Procedure

Respondents were given an informed consent form and told the data collection procedure, confidentiality and anonymity, and other ethical considerations.

Upon approval of the request, the researcher conducted one-on-one interviews with strict obedience to IATF protocols. Interviewing is a particularly effective technique for collecting data about the lived experience of participants (Knox & Burkard, 2009).

Additional data were also gathered using other techniques, such as focus group discussions, journaling, and video recordings.

Then, the recorded interview was encoded, themed, and interpreted thoroughly to obtain accurate, necessary data based on the participants' perspectives. Finally, participants were provided with an electronic/hard copy of their transcribed interview to safeguard accuracy. They were asked to verify correctness, clarify any discrepancies, and further remark on the inquiry.

Data Analysis Procedure

Colazzi's (1978) phenomenology data analysis model highlights abstract patterns and describes the process I chose as I prepared for my investigation. The following steps will guide me for data processing:

1. The researcher thoroughly read and reread the transcribed interviews to identify with the data and acquire a sense of each individual and their background and experiences.
2. From the transcripts, the researcher identified significant statements which pertain directly to the phenomenon.
3. The researcher then developed interpretive meanings of each of the significant statements. Finally, the researcher reread the research protocols to ensure the original description is evident in the interpretive meanings.
4. The interpretive meanings were arranged into clusters, which allowed themes to emerge. The researcher sought validation, avoided repetitive themes, and noted any discrepancies during the process.
5. The themes were then integrated into a detailed description. The researcher also referred the theme clusters back to the protocols to substantiate them.
6. Then, the researcher produced a concise statement of the detailed description and provided essential information of identification, also referred to as the overall essence of the experience.

7. The reduced statements of the detailed description were presented to the study's participants to verify the conclusions and the development of the essence statement. If discrepancies were noted, the researcher would go back through the significant statements, interpretive meanings, and themes to address the stated concerns. (pp.48-71)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The findings of the study were presented in this section. These findings were derived from the interviews conducted among the twenty (20) Junior High School (JSH) students of COBNHSJHS and BNHS-JHS from grades 7-10 for the School Year 2021-2022. This study was specifically designed to describe the lived experiences of the public junior high school students who undertook Modular Distance learning modality which started in SY 2020-2021.

Based on the interviews with the participants of the study, five themes emerged to describe the lived experiences of COBNHS-JHS and BNHS-JHS students under Modular Distance Learning (MDL) modality. These are: (1) transfer of knowledge; (2) communication issues; (3) study mindset; (4) quality of assessment; and (5) Physio-emotional Well-being. These themes could be directly traced to those that were attributable to the students and the significant people around them.

Theme Cluster: Transfer of Knowledge

Transfer of knowledge is a “cognitive” practice where a learner’s mastery of a topic or concept enables them to apply that knowledge in another context, thus is often considered a hallmark of true learning (Barnett and Ceci, 2002).

In this study, “transfer of knowledge” is expressed in the following sub-themes: difficulty in following instructions, complexity of topics, and learning is not effective.

Table 1:

Theme	Sub-theme	Illustrative statement
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transfer of knowledge	difficulty in following instructions	<p>Participant 1-A: <i>“Walang teacher na magpapaliwanag sa gagawin kaya ang hirap intindihin”</i></p> <p>Participant 4-B: <i>“ Wala akong mapagtanungan. Nagagalit ang Tatay ko pag nagtatanong ako kasi di</i></p>
		<p><i>naman daw siya nag-aral, gayundin si Nanay.”</i></p> <p>Participant 8-A: <i>“Sana palagi andyan si Ate o Kuya para mapagtanungan. Kaso madalas me kasamang hampas o batok bago ako turuan.”</i></p> <p>Participant 5-B: <i>“Puro activity lang po ang laman, wala man lang paliwanag, nakakatamad po tuloy sagutan.”</i></p>
	complexity of topics	<p>Participant 3-B: <i>“Wala halos ako natutunan dahil ang hirap ng mga tanong lalo na sa Science at Math. Konti lang ang discussion tapos ang daming activity na dapat sagutan.”</i></p> <p>Participant 10-A: <i>“Wala naman sa discussion yung binigay na activity, ang layo kaya papano ko sasagutan, kaya ayun hindi na lang ako nagpasa, bahala na.”</i></p>
	learning is not effective	<p>Participant 7-B: <i>“Hindi ko nga alam kung tama ba ang ginawa ko sa activity kasi hindi naman bumalik sa akin activity sheets ko para malaman ko kung tama nga ba mga sagot ko.”</i></p> <p>Participant 9-A: <i>“Natutuwa nga po ako e, kasi me grade ako sa English kahit na hindi ako ang nagsagot. Nagpatulong ako ke nanay kasi nahihirapan ako intindihin ang mga activity.”</i></p>

Issues with communication may arise in any instance of our lives. There is a high probability that one misunderstands or misinterprets others which can lead to conflict or fight.

According to Enke and Borchers (2019), conflicts may occur because of miscommunication making it more challenging. “Communication Issues” in this study are expressed in two subthemes: availability at all times, unresponsiveness, and shyness/reluctance.

Table 2:

Theme	Sub-theme	Illustrative statements
Communication Issues	Availability at all times	Participant 5-A: <i>“Pag nagtext ako kay Ma’am ngayon bukas na siya sumasagot dahil busy o kaya man tulog na siya. Mas masarap kasi sa gabi mag-sagot tulog na mga nakababata kong kapatid. Sana gising din pag gabi teacher ko.”</i> Participant 9-B: <i>“Wala po akong load pangtext kay Ma’am kaya po hindi ko matanong pag nagsasagot ako ng modules.”</i> Participant 8-B: <i>“Sumasama po ako maglaba kay Nanay kaya pag naghomes visit si Ma’am wala po ako kaya hindi po ako makapagpaturo sa mga bahaging hirap ako.”</i>
	Unresponsiveness	Participant 6-B: <i>“Hindi sumasagot ang teacher ko sa mga tanong ko.”</i> Participant 10-B: <i>“Wala update ang Ma’am ko kung pasado ba ako o hindi. Tapos nakapagpasa na ako output pero sinabi ni Ma’am wala daw ako pinasa.”</i>

	Shyness/reluctance	Participant 1-B: <i>“Nahihiya po ako magtext kay Sir, baka sabihin po ang hina ko umintindi. Madali lang naman daw po yung activity.”</i> Participant 2-B: <i>“Kahit gusto ko sagutan agad, nahihiya akong makipag-usap o magpaturo.”</i>
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Theme Cluster: Study Mindset

Some students commented that reading and answering modules made them learn and focused; they felt responsible for the learning outcomes. Those who had this responsibility appeared to have a more positive experience. A growth mindset focuses students on learning, rather than simply performing well (Mangels et al. 2006). “Study Mindset” came up with two sub-themes: autonomy; and resourcefulness.

Table 3:

Theme	Sub-theme	Illustrative statement
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Study Mindset	autonomy	<p>Participant 2-A: <i>“Mas madali para sa akin ang pagbabasa at pagsagot ng modules/activity sheets kasi mahilig naman talaga ako magbasa. Wala pang magulong classmates na nabubiwisit habang nagcoconcentrate ako sa pagsosolve.”</i> Participant 4-A: <i>“Mas gusto ko ang modular kasi hindi ako kailangan gumising ng maaga at magworry dahil late na ako sa unang klase ko.”</i> Participant 7-A: <i>“Mas nachallenge ako na mag-aral mag-isa kaya okay lang magmodular ako. Akin pa ang oras ko, mas madami oras ako pwede maglaro at magbonding sa pamilya.”</i></p>
	resourcefulness	<p>Participant 6-A: <i>“Mas gusto ko po modular kasi pwede kong gawin ang mga outputs bago dumating ang deadline.”</i></p>
		<p>Participant 3-B: <i>“Magaling ang ate ko kaya sa kanya ako nagpapaturo, mataas palagi ang grade ko.”</i> Participant 3-A: <i>“Natuto akong magresearch sa google.”</i> Participant 5-A: <i>“Naginstall ako ng app kung saan mas mapapadali ang pagresearch at pagsagot ko sa mga activities.”</i></p>

	Procrastination	<p>Participant 5-B: <i>“Mas gusto ko po yung malapit na ang deadline saka ako magsasagot, ganundin naman po di ba.”</i> Participant 1-A: <i>“Natatamad na po ako magsagot lalo pag hindi na sumagot teacher ko. Kumokopya na lang po ako sa kapitbahay namin.”</i></p> <p>Participant 9-A: <i>“Nakakatamad magbasa. mas gusto ko yung me nakikita at napapakinggan ako. Saka na ako babawi.”</i></p>
	Cheating	<p>Participant 5-A: <i>“Itatype ko lang sa google lilitaw na ang sagot (ngingiti) bakit pa ako papakahirap.”</i></p> <p>Participant 9-B: <i>“Kumokopya na lang po ako sa kaklase ko pag nagpunta ako sa kanila, kaya man e si Lola o Ate na ang bahala sumagot, di naman malalaman ni Ma’am e.”</i></p> <p>Participant 10-A: <i>“Me sagot naman sa likod ng module, kinokopya ko na lang.”</i> (sabay tumawa nang mahina at tingin sa gilid)</p>

Theme Cluster: Quality of Assessment

Assessment, a process of collecting and interpreting evidence of student progress to inform reasoned judgments about what a student or group of students knows relative to the learning goals (National Research Council, 2001) was affected greatly because of the pandemic. Since DepEd did not require students to have quarterly assessment due to academic ease, there were only two components where grades are solved: written outputs and performance tasks. “Quality of

Assessment” is expressed in the following sub-themes: Grades not equating competence, Unreliability of Scores, and Apathy.

Table 4:

Theme	Sub-theme	Illustrative Statement
Quality of Assessment	grades not equating competence	Participant 6-A: <i>“Sa aking palagay, hindi nagmatch ang effort ko at ang grade na binigay sa akin kasi ang dami kong sinagutan at tama naman lahat pero 90% lng ang grade ko.”</i> Participant 7-B: <i>“Dahil hindi nga po bumalik sa akin yung mga sinagutan ko, hindi ako sigurado kung natuto ba talaga ako.”</i>
	unreliability of scores	Participant 10-B: <i>“Mababa ang nakuha kong grade sa mga subjects na nawala ang mga outputs ko.”</i>
	apathy	Participant 8-B: <i>“Wala naman ako pakialam ano man ang grades ko. Ang mahalaga e natutulungan ko si nanay maghanapbuhay, nagkakaopera pa ako.”</i> Participant 10-A: <i>“E di umulit na lang sa isang taon pag me face to face na.”</i>

Theme Cluster: Physio-emotional and Well-being:

For holistic learning to be developed, both our physical and mental health have to be nurtured as well. Stoddard (2019) asserted that emotions have an impact on our physical health, this direct interaction is imperative. One’s “Physio-emotional Well-being” has two sub-themes:

Stress and Anxiety.

Theme	Sub-theme	Illustrative Statement
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Physio-emotional and Wellbeing	Stress	<p>Participant 10-B: <i>“Nakakastress lalo na ng mawala mga outputs ko at kelangan ko ulitin para lang makacomply or else bababa ang grades ko.”</i> Participant 6-B: <i>“Hindi ko alam kung susundin ko magulang ko na huminto na lang kesa mahirapan ako.”</i></p> <p>Participant 7-B: <i>“Nakakastress kasi dapat ibinabalik ang mga activity sheets na sinagutan para alam ko bakit ganun lang nakuha ko.”</i></p>
	Anxiety	<p>Participant 4-A: <i>“Nagkaroon ako ng anxiety attacks simula ng pandemic kasi hindi na kami nagkikita-kita ng mga kaibigan ko.”</i> Participants 1-B and 2-B: <i>“Hindi naman po kasi mas gusto ko po mag-isa.”</i></p> <p>Participant 4-B: <i>“Mahirap po ang nasa bahay lang kasi sa halip makapag-aral kailangan ko tumulong sa mga gawaing bahay kahit na masama na ang loob ko dahil lagi akong inuutusan.”</i></p>

Correspondingly, it could be seen from the statements above that most of the students had a hard time answering their modules or did not have enough time to accomplish all the activities within the given schedule or deadline. Receiving at least 8 modules in all subjects with 5 or more activities really took a toll on their physio-emotional well-being as well. For instance, in solving math problems, a detailed explanation or in-depth discussion is needed to be able to comprehend or analyze what is being asked, yet there was just little to none. In English 10, some had lengthy readings and there were terms that they never understood. Additionally, most of the students could

not answer their modules independently and needed the assistance of their family members, relatives, friends or classmates. Teachers were approachable but not all the time they were available to entertain queries particularly at night or weekends.

As some participants stated that they formed a bond with their parents and/or siblings as they spend more time together answering modules, some parents were not always there for them because they were busy working or attending to their family's needs. Consequently, this set up didn't produce a positive impact in the completion and submission of modules at all times. Students are lucky if their parents or family are supportive, while students without family assistance endured alone.

While it has been evident that learning remains possible, issues with communication, physio-emotional and well-being, quality of assessment, study mindset, and transfer of knowledge remain adamant that contributed to learners' perspective of modular distance learning as difficult. SY 2020-2021 continuing to SY 2021-2022 brought several arguments on its effect on students' mental health and possibility of ineffective learning, since only the cognitive aspect has been touched, leaving both psychomotor (collaborative) and affective facets of learning. Overall, they still prefer face-to-face classes because they believe that with the presence of their teachers and classmates, they can learn better.

CONCLUSION

The Covid-19 pandemic spawned numerous challenges in the sector of education, but with the goals of UNESCO and DepEd to promote continuous relevant, inclusive education, administrators along with teachers reshaped how learners would study as schools were closed as a preventive measure amidst the threat of the pandemic. However, the main concern lies in whether or not the students learned effectively based on MELCs in answering their modules. The use of

modular distance learning did not guarantee acquiring the expected competencies period considering the diversity of our learners. Thus, studying during this was indeed very challenging for most, especially in difficult subjects like Mathematics and Science, both in learning the content and in answering the activities.

In general, participants have experienced immense struggle in modular distance learning due to various issues that surround them at the time. The pandemic made learning more challenging than it already is. There are many difficulties that were encountered due to the abruptness of the worldwide disaster and the overall unpreparedness to respond to the problem of ongoing education while being on lock down. Many internal and external factors affected the mental and emotional state of the students and the suitability of the learning environment they have at home. But despite the difficulties, students still learned to adapt to changes and overcome the challenges brought upon by the pandemic with the help of their family, teachers, and friends.

With this, MDL has many implications as to learning proficiency and dispositions of students who undertook this modality of learning. Findings revealed that disposition towards learning is a compelling factor that is related with learners' proficiency or performance. Learners who are more enthusiastic in answering modules have a better chance of improving their performance, while anxious learners produce inferior outcomes which could result to distressing study mindset after. Hence, learners must recognize the advantages of MDL as supplement to conventional instruction.

RECOMMENDATION

Amidst the current crisis brought by the pandemic, the shift to modular distance learning can be formidable for educators as they continue to seek best ways to better serve students and families with equitable access to resources and instruction needed to support students. With the factors that emerge in this study, it is recommended that the current system concerning distance learning be

reexamined in depth in order to compensate for the inadequate learning experience of the students. Preparations may be more thorough to implement the new teaching and learning approach procedures properly. The use of diversified teaching strategies may be implemented and strengthened in order to accommodate the learning needs of the students depending on the aptitude and environment. providing a clearer sense of direction for the intended learning can tremendously help in coping instead of being confined to the passive role of receiving knowledge. Thus, learning activities and assessments need to be more student-centered, leading to independent thinking and lessons be designed, leveraging appropriate tools and instructional models that make students more engaged in the learning process.

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APPENDIX

INSTRUMENT:

Name (optional): _____ Grade and Section (optional) :

_____ School: _____

SY: 2021-2022**Interview Guide:**

1. Paano mo ilalarawan ang iyong karanasan sa pag-aaral sa pamamagitan ng paggamit ng modyul? Maaari mo itong ibahagi.

2. Ano ang mga problema na iyong naranasan sa paggamit ng modyul? Ano ang iyong ginawa upang malunasan ito?

3. Maaari mo bang ilarawan ang iyong “study routine” sa bahay habang may pandemya?

4. Ano ang iyong nagustuhan sa “modular learning”? Magbigay ng halimbawa.

5. Ano naman ang iyong hindi nagustuhan? Magbigay ng halimbawa.

6. Ano ang naging epekto ng modular learning sa iyo? Sa mental, sosyal at pampamilyang aspeto.

7. Mayroon ka bang gustong mabago o imungkahi batay sa iyong karanasan?
